

MODALITY-BASED ASSESSMENT PRACTICES AND STRATEGIES DURING PANDEMIC

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ABSTRACT

The success of educational activities can be determined through assessment. It is the vital part of the whole educative process whether the learning competencies are attained or not. During the arrival of COVID-19, education is one of the most affected since face-to-face classes are prohibited to control the spread of the virus. As a response, educational setting shifted to align on the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan amidst pandemic. This research investigates on how teachers go along with the transition of assessing student's learning from what is usually conducted on face-to-face classes. A survey questionnaire was distributed to 55 teachers from Zamboanga City and Zamboanga Sibugay to collect data about the assessment practices and strategies based on the modalities of learning used by the teachers to evaluate students learning during pandemic. The research investigates to find out the efficiency of the different modular assessment practices such as, Quiz, Summative test, Activity sheet, and modular assessment strategies which include, Reflection Paper, Specialized Projects and Oral Recitation through Call. The research also examines the application of blended assessment practices such as Output Compilation, Competency Learned Journal and Process-Based Assessment through online interview, at the same time blended assessment strategies which includes Online Paperless Test, Video Recorded Demonstration and Live Video Call Assessment. This research is significant for educational institutions and stakeholders to find out the relevance and efficacy of the different assessment practices and strategies applied by the teachers during pandemic in evaluate students learning.

Keywords: COVID-19 Pandemic, Assessment Practices, Assessment Strategies, Modality-Based Assessment